

Human Rights Approach to Education- Essential Need

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“Human rights are the result of humanity's increasing and persistent demand for dignity, respect, justice, protection and freedom--all needed for a decent human existence.”

***Abstract:** An attempt is made in this paper to analyse the importance of human rights education in the present scenario. The analysis focus and justified why the analysis is taken up with help of violations taken place even sixty years after its issue, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights is still more a dream than reality. Regarding India, as illiteracy rate is more, people who do not go to educational institutions are remained unaware of their rights as born as human beings, and they should be educated at such places where they work.*

Key words: Human rights, Universal Declaration, Violation, gender, equality, fundamental freedom

Introduction:

The contemporary conception of human rights has historical roots. Rousseau, Socrates, and Plato in the West, and Manu, Vyasadeva, Gandhi, Aurobindo, and others in India have enunciated principles of human rights. Important milestones in the struggle for human rights are the struggle between the British crown and Parliament, the French revolution, the struggle for American independence, the Russian revolution, and the adoption of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights by the United Nations on 10 December 1948. The Declaration symbolized the beginning of the international human rights movement. In 1959, children's rights to life, education, health, protection, and development were proclaimed in the Declaration of the Rights of the Child. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights embodies a set of guarantees enabling one

- Not just to live but to live with dignity;
- To develop fully and use one's human qualities, intelligence, talents, and conscience; and
- To satisfy one's physical, mental, social, and spiritual needs.

“All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights”. So stated by Article 1 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1948. This is what the Indians have been preaching since times immemorial as it has become the immemorial customs of our nation .Human Rights are a fundamental value. Upholding human rights values in every aspect is firmly in our tradition. But the values that we stand for – freedom, human rights, the rule of law – are all universal values. Given the choice, people all over the world want them. But it is regretting that India who was once looked up by whole world as the pioneer of these values is now pleading in lowly dust of atrocities and human rights abuse. Human rights abuse is sadly a reality in Indian society; it is not just an affront to the values of tolerance, freedom and justice that underpin our society. It is also a tragic waste of human potential.

It is high time to send human rights back to school. Not just for a while, in a single Classroom or as one part of the curriculum. But as an ever present influence that transforms the lives of everyone involved in school life. When human rights come into class, onto the playground and into the hearts and minds of young people, Attitudes and behaviors begin to change. The values and principles of human rights start to direct the thoughts and actions of the school community. With human rights as an instinctive frame of reference, inclusion, tolerance, and respect for diversity enter into school life, leaving little room for harassment and discrimination. That's how our human connection deepens, widens and gets cemented. Hence, the objective

of this paper is to give a thoughtful consideration to the various aspects and concepts of the Human Rights education.

The Need for Human rights Education

It is universally accepted that education is the best source of social mobility, equality, and empowerment, both at the individual and collective levels. Further, it is considered as a precondition for a healthy democratic society. It is thus important that education include the study of peace, human rights, and democracy as essential to society's development.

The World Conference on Human Rights considers human rights education, training and public information essential for the promotion and achievement of stable and harmonious relations among communities and for fostering mutual understanding, tolerance and peace.

States should strive to eradicate illiteracy and should direct education towards the full development of the human personality and to the strengthening of respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms. The World Conference on Human Rights calls on all States and institutions to include human rights, humanitarian law, democracy and rule of law as subjects in the curricula of all learning institutions in formal and non-formal settings.

Human rights education should include peace, democracy, development and social justice, as set forth in international and regional human rights instruments, in order to achieve common understanding and awareness with a view to strengthening universal commitment to human rights.

Human rights education, training and public information are, therefore, necessary and essential for the promotion and achievement of stable and harmonious relations among the communities and for fostering mutual understanding, tolerance and peace. Through the learning of human rights as a way of life, fundamental change could be brought about to eradicate poverty, ignorance, prejudices, and discrimination based on sex, caste, religion, and disability and other status amongst the people.

Educational Policies and Human Rights

The reports of various Education Commissions and the statement of educational policy have articulated the importance of the right to education and education in human rights as part of the effort to reform and develop education. They assign special status in the national educational system to women, scheduled castes, scheduled tribes, minorities, and the handicapped, and emphasize values education. They also define the basic components of the core curriculum, which reflects some important human rights concerns.

The National Curriculum Framework is provided for by the 1986 National Education Policy. It covers core elements that cut across narrow subject boundaries and is designed to promote values such as India's common cultural heritage, egalitarianism, democracy, secularism, equality of the sexes, observance of small-family norms, and inculcation of scientific temper, among other things.

Objectives of Human Rights Education

- Enhance the knowledge and understanding of human rights.
- Foster attitudes of tolerance, respect, solidarity, and responsibility.
- Develop awareness of how human rights can be translated into social and political reality.
- Develop skills for protecting human rights.
 - Acquire the knowledge & skills related to human rights
- Develop values and attitudes that lead to changed behavior
- Reach out beyond school to get involved with the community
- Act to motivate meaningful change

Methodology, Approaches, and Strategies

- **The formal curriculum:** Schools may choose to examine their present curriculums and identify areas where themes and elements of human rights education already exist. Human rights education is considered the most important part of the core curriculum of good general education.
- **The informal curriculum:** Human rights education can also be promoted through the extra-curricular and co-curricular activities of the school.
- **The hidden curriculum:** Human rights education should also address the far reaching hidden curriculum of the school to create a school atmosphere that truly reflects respect for human rights. Values, attitudes, knowledge, and patterns of behavior should be integrated into the students' personal experiences in order to help them view reality critically.

Basic Approach

The basic approach to human rights education in schools is to integrate it into various subjects and not treat it as a separate area of study. It also requires a multidisciplinary approach. The issue of human rights is inextricably linked with other major curricular issues. The National Curriculum Framework for School Education (NCERT 2000) recommends the integration of various curricular concerns:

The curriculum development process is often influenced by a 'panic approach' in which the local, national or international developments with some socio-economic and political bearing influence the decisions concerning the curriculum without prior, careful and structured planning. This 'panic approach' of including new and temporal curricular concerns may often lead to an overloading of the curriculum. At a time when concerns such as 'literacy', 'family system', 'neighborhood education', 'environmental education', 'consumer education', 'tourism education', 'AIDS education', 'human rights education', 'legal literacy', 'peace education', 'population education', 'migration education', 'global education' and 'safety education' are making a case for separate place in the school curriculum, the best approach would be to integrate these ideas and concepts, after a careful analysis in the existing areas of learning. This should constitute a realistic approach -- meaningful, responsive, and result oriented. Human rights are itself an educational conception involving human interaction inside and outside school.

Human rights Education in India

It may be said that in India that the content of human rights education is not different to what was taught by way of religion, be it Hinduism, Buddhism, Christianity or Islam. There is lot of truth in that statement. However, while teaching religions we confined the obligations arising from these doctrines only to their followers. Human rights could bring in a universal aspect to moral and ethical education. And we in our divided societies are in great need of this. On the other hand in the context of rapid secularization we could still retain a basic common ground for respect for each other.

Indian textbooks barely mention human rights. Indirect references to human rights are included in the Directive Principles of the Constitution of India and in civics and history textbooks. Most universities in India do not offer human rights education, although some have three-month to one-year postgraduate courses on human rights. Section 12(h) of the Protection of Human Rights Act, 1993, requires the Commission "to spread human rights literacy among various sections of society and promote awareness.

How can HRE transform a school Human Rights Friendly?

A Human Rights Friendly School is where human rights are learned, taught, practiced, respected, protected and promoted. A school that is 'friendly' to human rights is one in which all are included yet every individual is unique. It is a place where human rights values are nurtured via the school curriculum, through relationships, within the school environment and in the way the school is governed. When human rights

spread through school life so completely, attitudes and behaviors are bound to change. Almost all schools have registered a reduction in disciplinary measures, an increase in attendance, positive shifts in classroom/playground relationships, and better peer/social interaction.

Benefits of becoming a human rights friendly school

1. Teacher report greater confidence in creating positive class room environment
2. Students develop a heightened awareness of social issues
3. Teachers and students experience an enhanced ability to work and learn collaboratively
4. Members of wider community get involved in school life
5. Students start to work towards positive change beyond the class room, beyond the School

From a school to a movement:

A Human Rights Friendly School is an empowering place where teaching replaces instruction, shared responsibility replaces authority, and guidelines replace rules. At such a school, Students enjoy the learning process because they feel empowered and secure to inquire, express their opinions and stand up for what they think is right. As Human Rights Friendly Schools send into the world, individuals who have an inbuilt understanding of living through the principles of human rights, wider circles of influence ripple out. A movement gains momentum. Meaningful change becomes possible.

Conclusion:

Over the last five decades, the process of internationalization and globalization of the concept of human rights has generated the movement "All Human Rights for All." In a complex country such as India, violations of human rights at all levels necessitate human rights education at all school levels in general and teacher education in particular. Human rights education must exert its influence from early childhood education onward and through a broad range of disciplines to build a human rights culture. Hence, greater commitment from all sectors and preparation of a sound, realistic plan of action can help us achieve human rights education for all and transform the human rights movement into a mass movement to achieve a better social order and peaceful living. Indeed, this is one of the greatest challenges in the 21st century.

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